

FORMULATION

Consider a penny-shaped crack that is originally located inside the composite and is perpendicular to the fiber axis. Under the applied stress along the fiber axis, the penny-shaped crack will grow in a concentric manner. The above three-dimensional crack propagation can be simulated by the two-dimensional model shown in Fig. 1 if one is allowed to extend the two-dimensional results into the three-dimensional one by taking the volume average concept. The similar concept was used in our previous work (6). We assume in the present model that the coated fiber is of the rectangular section as shown in Fig. 2 where the fiber diameter is $2r_f$ and the thickness of the coating is r_c . The plastic deformation is assumed to take place along the interface adjacent to the crack plane. The fracture toughness of the composite can be considered to consist of two parts, the elastic strain energy release rate and plastic work dissipated along the interface.

Elastic Strain Energy Release Rate

If one can assume the iso-strain condition for the two-dimensional crack in a composite, then the energy release rate of the crack of $2a$ in the composite, \bar{G} can be obtained as

$$\bar{G} = \left\{ V_f \left(\frac{E_f}{E} G_f \right)^{1/2} + V_m \left(\frac{E_m}{E} G_m \right)^{1/2} + V_c \left(\frac{E_c}{E} G_c \right)^{1/2} \right\}^2 \quad (1)$$

where V and E are the volume fraction and Young's modulus and the subscripts f , m and c denote the fiber, matrix and coating, respectively, and

$$\bar{E} = V_f E_f + V_m E_m + V_c E_c \quad (2)$$

$$G_\alpha = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\Delta a} \int_0^{\Delta a} \sigma_y^\alpha v^\alpha dr \quad \text{for } \alpha = f, m \text{ and } c. \quad (3)$$

In eq. (3), t is the thickness of a plate containing such a crack, σ_y is the component of stress perpendicular to the crack plane and v is the crack tip opening displacement. The schematical models for G_f , G_c , G_m and \bar{G} are shown in Figs. 3a, 3b, 3c and 3d, respectively. It can be easily found that \bar{G} in eq. (1) is equivalent to

$$\bar{G} = \frac{\pi(1-\nu^2)\bar{\sigma}^2 a}{\bar{E}} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\sigma} = V_f \sigma_f + V_m \sigma_m + V_c \sigma_c$ (see also Fig. 3), and the Poisson's ratio ν is assumed as:

$$\nu = \nu_m = \nu_f = \nu_c. \quad (5)$$

Plastic Work Along the Interface

The analytical model for the computation of the plastic work along the coating-matrix interface is shown in Fig. 4 where the crack tip is located between the just-broken fiber and the adjacent fiber in the right. The plastic work along the interface U_1 can be given by

$$U_1 = 2\pi d_f y_o \tau_y \delta_o \quad (6)$$

where d_f is the fiber diameter, τ_y is the interfacial shear stress and is assumed to be constant over the distance y_o and δ_o is the total crack opening displacement and can be given by the sum of the displacements for the following three cases:

- (i) the crack opening displacement when the fiber in the crack plane fails (Fig. 5a), δ_1

- (ii) the crack opening displacement when the averaged force in the fiber, $\pi d_f^2 \sigma_f / 4$ is applied to the crack surface (Fig. 5b), δ_2
- (iii) the crack opening displacement when τ_y is applied along the interface over y_0 (Fig. 5c), δ_3 .

The crack opening displacement, in general, can be expressed by

$$\delta = \frac{K_I}{\mu} \sqrt{\frac{b_0}{2\pi}} \frac{k+1}{2} \quad (7)$$

where μ is the shear modulus of the matrix, $k = 3-4\nu$ for plane strain condition, b_0 is the distance between the fiber and crack tip and is taken as the spacing between the two neighboring fibers. The stress intensity K_I is given by (8) as

$$K_I = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\sigma \pi a} & \text{for } \delta_1 \\ -\frac{\sigma_f \pi d_f^2}{4t \sqrt{\pi a}} \sqrt{\frac{a+x_0}{a-x_0}} & \text{for } \delta_2 \\ -\frac{\pi d_f y_0 \tau_y}{\sqrt{\pi a}} \sqrt{\frac{a+x_0}{a-x_0}} & \text{for } \delta_3 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $x_0 = a - b_0$.

The value of y_0 can be determined from the fracture criterion of the fiber:

$$\frac{\pi d_f^2 \sigma_{fc}}{4} = \frac{\pi d_f^2 \sigma_f}{4} + \pi d_f y_0 \tau_y \quad (9)$$

where σ_{fc} is the fiber breaking stress. From eqs. (6) and (9),

$$U_1 = \pi d_f^2 (\sigma_{fc} - \sigma_f) \delta_0 / 2. \quad (10)$$

Fracture Toughness for the Penny-Shaped Crack

Since the penny-shaped crack is assumed to propagate in a concentric manner, the ratio of the sectional area of the fibers swept by the crack and the total crack area reaches to the volume fraction of the fiber. Therefore, if the radius of the penny-shaped crack is greater than a certain value, the elastic energy release rate \bar{G} defined for the plane strain condition previously mentioned can be considered to be applicable to the penny-shaped crack front in composite. Moreover, if the Griffith theory is used as a fracture criterion, the relation between the energy release rate \bar{G} of the penny-shaped crack and the radius of the crack is also given by eq. (4).

The total plastic work for the penny-shaped crack sweeping the ring region R which has n fibers is nU_1 (eq. (10)). Therefore, when the penny-shaped crack propagates the region without fibers, the fracture toughness G is G . When the crack propagates the region with fibers, the fracture toughness for the composite becomes

$$G = \frac{1}{\pi(r_2^2 - r_1^2)} \left(\int_{r_1}^{r_2} \bar{G} 2\pi r \, dr + nU_1 \right) \quad (11)$$

where r_2 and r_1 are the outer and inner radius of the ring region with fibers, respectively, as shown in Fig. 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to estimate the fracture toughness of the metal matrix composite

with a penny-shaped crack, we use the following material properties (7) of Boron fiber reinforced aluminum with coating zone of silicon carbide: $E_m = 71 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$, $E_f = E_c = 400 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$, $r_f = 75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$ and $r_c = 2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$. By adopting the fiber volume fraction of $V_f = 0.3$ and 0.5 , we obtain $V_c = 0.016$ and $V_m = 0.684$, and $V_c = 0.027$ and $V_m = 0.473$. In order to estimate the fracture toughness, we need to know the data of the fracture strength σ_{fc} of the fiber with coating zone. Ochiai and Murakami (9) performed the tensile test of the fiber with brittle coating zone for measuring σ_{fc} . According to their results on Boron fiber, the fiber has the critical energy release rate of $G_{fc} = 15.8 \text{ Jm}^{-2}$, and the crack size a_o in the coating zone has a minimum value of $0.28 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$ above which σ_{fc} decreases with increasing a_o . The width of the coating zone used in the present study is $2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$. The coating zone has

$$\frac{1}{E_f} \left(\frac{\pi d_f y_o y}{\pi d_f^2 / 4} \right)^2 - \frac{\pi d_f^2}{4} y_o = \frac{4 \pi \tau y_o^3}{E_f} U_2. \quad (12)$$

However, the value of U_2 is very small, compared with U_1 . For instance, when $V_f = 0.3$ and $a = 4.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}$, U_1 is $9.17 \times 10^{-6} \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$ and U_2 is $3.45 \times 10^{-8} \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}$. Hence, U_2 is neglected in Fig. 7. It follows from Fig. 7 that the smaller the volume fraction of fiber is, the tougher the metal matrix composite becomes. The value of the macroscopic fracture energy G_o of the metal matrix composite specimen can be computed as

$$G_o = \pi \alpha a_o^3 \quad (13)$$

where a_o is the radius of the specimen of cylindrical type and α is the tangent of the \bar{G} - a curve in Fig. 7.

CONCLUSIONS

An attempt is made of a theoretical study on the prediction of the fracture toughness of the metal matrix composite with brittle coating zone. In order to estimate the fracture toughness, the elastic strain energy release rate of the metal matrix composite with coating zone and the plastic work done on the matrix by the fiber are mainly considered. For given material data of Boron fiber reinforced aluminum, the fracture toughness is given as a function of crack length. Moreover, the Kendall model, after it is extended to a three-plane composite material, has proved to be a powerful method in the fracture analysis of composite.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present research was partially supported by the National Science Foundation (Grant No. CME-7918249) and Honda R & D Company.

REFERENCES

1. Kelly, A. "Interface Effects and the Work of Fracture of a Fibrous Composite," Proc. Roy. Soc. London, Vol. A319, 1970, pp. 95-116.
2. Piggot, M. R. "Theoretical Estimate of Fracture Toughness of Fibrous Composites," J. Mater. Sci., Vol. 5, 1970, pp. 669-675.
3. Phillips, D. C., and Tetelman, A. S. "The Fracture Toughness of Fibre Composites," Composites, Vol. 3, 1972, pp. 216-223.
4. Murphy, M. C., and Outwater, J. O. "The Toughness of Reinforced Plastics," 28th Ann. Tech. Conf., Soc. Plastic Industry, Washington, D.C., 1973, Sect. 17A, pp. 1-6.
5. Kendall, K. "Transition Between Cohesive and Interfacial Failure," Proc. Roy. Soc. London, Vol. A344, 1975, pp. 287-302.
6. Ishikawa, H., Chou, T. W., and Taya, M. "Prediction of Failure Modes in Unidirectional Short-Fiber Composites," J. Mater. Sci., Vol. 17, 1982, pp. 832-842.
7. Kreider, K. G., and Prewo, K. M. "Boron-Reinforced Aluminum," Composite Materials, Vol. 4, edited by K. G. Kreider, Academic Press, 1974,

pp. 399-471.

8. Tada, H., Paris, P., and Irwin, G. The Stress Analysis of Cracks Handbook, Del. Research Corporation, 1973.

9. Ochiai, S., and Murakami, Y. "Tensile Strength of Composites with Brittle Reaction Zones at Interfaces," J. Mater. Sci., Vol. 14, 1979, pp. 831-840.

Fig. 1. The analytical model.

Fig. 2. A penny-shaped crack in a composite. The shaded area is the yielded matrix.

Fig. 3. Four cases of two-dimensional crack in (a) fiber, (b) coating, (c) matrix and (d) the material of their averaged properties.

Fig. 4. The plastic work in the matrix along the interface.

Fig. 5. Crack opening displacements by (a) the fiber failure (b) the averaged fiber force (c) the resultant force of the interface stress.

Fig. 6. The ring region with fiber swept by the propagating penny-shaped crack.

Fig. 7. Fracture toughness \bar{G} of a Boron-reinforced aluminum as a function of the crack radius a for $V_f = 0.3$ and 0.5 .